

Stability of Chromium Chelates of 8-Quinolinol-5-sulphonate

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The interaction of Cr(III) ions and 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate has been studied by the potentiometric method. Formation and hydrolysis constants have been calculated for chelates containing 1:1 and 2:1 ratios of ligand to metal ion. The values of these constants are: $\log K_{CrA} = 10.99$, $\log K_{CrA_2} = 10.06$, $-\log K_{Cr(OH)A} = 5.14$, $-\log K_{Cr(OH)A_2} = 7.05$, $-\log K_{Cr(OH)A_3} = 9.65$.

8-Hydroxyquinoline has been used as a precipitating reagent in the estimation of a large number of metal ions. On the other hand, the sulphonic acid derivative of the reagent would be expected to form the metal chelates, solubilised by the sulphonate group. In view of the considerable interest¹⁻³ in the investigation of the interaction of the metal ions and 8-hydroxyquinoline-5 sulphonic acid and in the determination of the stability constants of the chelates, it has been considered worthwhile to study the interaction of chromium(III) and the ligand and to determine the stability and hydrolysis constants of the chelates formed under conditions such that the maximum co-ordination number of the metal ion could not reach. As reported in the interaction of chromium and EDTA⁶ and a number of other ligands, in this case also there was no appreciable reaction at the room temperature, even after keeping for hours, probably due to nonavailability of the free chromium ions in the solution. Before carrying out potentiometric titrations, therefore the reaction mixtures had to be heated when a red colour was developed, indicating complex-forming reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of chrome alum and potassium chloride were prepared from B.D.H. Analytical materials. 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (B.D.H.), H₂A, was recrystallised twice from water and then converted into monopotassium salt solution by addition of the requisite amount of a standard KOH solution.

The reaction mixtures containing 1:1 and 2:1 molar ratios of ligand to the metal ions were heated on a steam bath for 4 hr., cooled, and made to 500 ml in such a manner that the resulting solutions were 0.1M with respect to KCl. The reaction mixture (200 ml) was taken in a titration cell and the H⁺-ion concentration was determined by

1. Nasanen and Vinitalo, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 112.
2. Albert, *Biochem. J.*, 1953, 54, 646.
3. Albert and Hampton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 606.
4. Mnsley and Mellor, *Austri. J. Sci. Res.*, 1949, A, 579.
5. Richard *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 81, 1033.
6. Flashohka, 'EDTA Titrations', Pergamon Press Ltd., London, 1956, p. 20.

a number of successive readings after each addition of small increments of 0.1M-KOH. The ionic strength was maintained relatively constant by using a medium containing 0.1M-KCl and low concentrations of the ligand and the metal ions. All the titrations were repeated, at least twice, to ensure reproducibility of the results.

pH measurements were carried out with a Cambridge pH-meter, standardised against a 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate, at the room temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ$).

Calculations for 1:1-Reaction Mixture

In the pH range studied, the chelate species, CrA^+ , and Cr(OH)A , were found to exist. The equilibria may be represented by

$$K_{\text{CrA}} = \frac{[\text{CrA}^+]}{[\text{Cr}^{3+}] [\text{A}^{2-}]} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

and

$$K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}} = \frac{[\text{Cr(OH)A}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{CrA}^+]} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

If T_A represents the total concentration of various ligand species and T_M , that of all the metal species and considering the hydrolysis of the chelate CrA to be negligible in the lower buffer region,

$$T_A = [\text{H}_2\text{A}] + [\text{HA}^-] + [\text{A}^{2-}] + [\text{CrA}^+] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$T_M = [\text{Cr}^{3+}] + [\text{CrA}^+] \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Total amount of titrable hydrogen is

$$(2-a)T_A = 2[\text{H}_2\text{A}] + [\text{HA}^-] + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-] \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where a = number of moles of base added per mole of ligand. If K_{a_1} , (1.445×10^{-4})² and K_{a_2} , (4.487×10^{-9})² denote dissociation constants of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (H_2A),

$$[\text{A}^{2-}] = \frac{(2-a)T_A - [\text{H}^+] + [\text{OH}^-]}{2 \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_{a_1} \cdot K_{a_2}} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_{a_2}}} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Combination of equations 1, 3, and 4 provides

$$K_{\text{CrA}} = \frac{T_A - [\text{A}^{2-}] X}{[\text{A}^{2-}]^2 X} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } X = 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_{a_1}} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_{a_1} \cdot K_{a_2}}$$

In the upper buffer region, consideration of the hydrolysis of the chelate (reaction ii) provides

$$T_{OH} \div [H^+] - [OH^-] = [Cr(OH)A] \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$$T_A = [CrA^+] + [Cr(OH)A] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

where T_{OH} = molar concentration of the base added; $m = 1$ (m = number of moles of base added per mole of the metal ion).

Combining equations 2, 8, and 9

$$K_{Cr(OH)A} = \frac{T_{OH} + [H^+] - [OH^-]}{T_A - T_{OH} - [H^+] + [OH^-]} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

After determining the values of K_{CrA} and $K_{Cr(OH)A}$, concentrations of the chelates CrA and $Cr(OH)A$ at various values of pH can be calculated under the experimental conditions.

Calculations for 2:1-Reaction Mixture ($T_A = 2T_M$)

In this case, the chelates CrA^+ and CrA_2^- were successively formed in the lower buffer region and the chelate CrA_2^- was found to hydrolyse in the upper buffer region. Thus in the lower buffer region, the equilibria may be represented by

$$K_{CrA} = \frac{[CrA^+]}{[Cr^{3+}][A^{2-}]} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

and

$$K_{CrA_2} = \frac{[CrA_2^-]}{[CrA^+][A^{2-}]} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

As in the previous case, the total concentrations of the ligand and metal species will be given by

$$T_A = [H_2A] + [HA^-] + [A^{2-}] + [CrA^+] + 2[CrA_2^-] \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

$$T_M = [Cr^{3+}] + [CrA^+] + [CrA_2^-] \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

The above equations afford the relationship:

$$K_{CrA_2} = \frac{b}{[A^{2-}]^3 \cdot X \cdot K_{CrA}} \quad (14)$$

where $b = T_A + T_M \cdot K_{CrA} \cdot [A^{2-}] - [A^{2-}] \cdot X (1 + [A^{2-}] K_{CrA})$.

Thus after determining K_{CrA} (equation 7), the value of K_{CrA_2} may be calculated and the equilibrium concentrations of the chelates CrA and CrA_2 may also be determined.

In the upper buffer region, the equilibria may be represented as

$$K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2} = \frac{[\text{Cr(OH)A}_2^{2-}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{CrA}_2^-]} \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

$$K_{\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_2} = \frac{[\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_2^{3-}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Cr(OH)A}_2^{2-}]} \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

If C_{OH} represents the molar concentration of the base added after $m = 2$,

$$C_{\text{OH}} + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-] = [\text{Cr(OH)A}_2^{2-}] + 2 [\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_2^{3-}] \quad \dots \quad (19)$$

$$T_{\text{M}} = [\text{CrA}_2^-] + [\text{Cr(OH)A}_2^{2-}] + [\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_2^{3-}] \quad \dots \quad (20)$$

From equations 15, 16, 17, and 18 it may be shown that

$$\text{where } y = K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2} \cdot x + K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2} \cdot K_{\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_2} \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

$$y = [\text{H}^+]^2 \frac{C_{\text{OH}} + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-]}{2T_{\text{M}} - C_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+] + [\text{OH}^-]}$$

$$x = [\text{H}^+] \frac{T_{\text{M}} - C_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+] + [\text{OH}^-]}{2T_{\text{M}} - C_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+] + [\text{OH}^-]}$$

Thus the plot of y against the corresponding values of x should afford a straight line, the slope of which will be equal to $K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2}$ and the intercept on y -axis will provide the value of $K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2} \cdot K_{\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_2}$.

After determining the values of the hydrolysis constants, the concentrations of the existing ionic species may be calculated.

DISCUSSION

Curve 1 (Fig. 1) for the potentiometric titration of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate in presence of equimolar concentration of chromium(III) ions shows a large depression of pH , indicating the reaction:

This chelation by donation of a lone pair of electrons from the hydroxyl oxygen makes the hydrogen atom more labile and acidic and thus the extent of lowering in the pH

of the system is a direct measure of the above type of chelation. It was therefore considered worthwhile to determine the formation constant of the chelate (equation 7).

TABLE I

KOH(ml)	..	0.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
pH	..	2.58	2.63	2.70	2.78	2.85	2.99
Log K_{CrA}	..	11.02	10.88	10.93	11.02	11.12	10.98

Mean of log K_{CrA} = 10.90 or K_{CrA} = 0.97×10^{10} .

The nature of the titration curve after $m=1$ indicates the reaction:

Attempts were therefore made to calculate the hydrolysis constant $K_{Cr(OH)A}$ for the reaction (equation 10). The values of this constant, calculated in the pH range 5.0 - 5.6, are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

KOH(ml)	..	11.5	12.0	12.5	13.0	13.5	14.0
pH	..	5.00	5.12	5.26	5.40	5.52	5.60
-Log $K_{Cr(OH)A}$	..	5.10	5.11	5.15	5.18	5.19	5.13

Mean of $-\log K_{Cr(OH)A}$ = 5.14 or $K_{Cr(OH)A}$ = 7.24×10^{-6} .

After determining the stability and hydrolysis constants of the chelate, concentrations of (I) and (II) at various values of pH could be calculated under the experimental conditions (curves 1 and 2, Fig. 2).

The increasing slope of the titration curve (curve 1, Fig. 1) after $m=2$ probably indicates further co-ordination of hydroxo group. But in this range the calculation could not be made due to appearance of a solid phase, yellowish green, at about $m=2$, although the precipitate had a slight tendency to pass into solution in strongly alkaline medium.

Curve 2 (Fig. 1) for the potentiometric titration of the reaction mixture, containing the ligand and metal ions in the molar ratio of 2 : 1, is throughout lower than curve 1, indicating further chelation. Inflection at about $m = 2$ corresponds to the formation of the 2 : 1 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate-chromium chelate in accordance with :

It was therefore considered of interest to determine the formation constant of the chelate. The value of $\bar{n}$ before the commencement of the potentiometric titration of the reaction mixture was found to be about 1.5. Attempts were therefore made to determine formation constants by the algebraic method (eq. 14), instead of Bjerrum's procedure.

FIG. 1. Potentiometric titrations of Cr(III) chelates of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate with KOH(0.1M) in 0.1M-KCl.

Curve 1: $4 \times 10^{-3}M$ in Cr(III) and $4 \times 10^{-3}M$ in ligand (HA).

Curve 2: $4 \times 10^{-3}M$ in Cr(III) and $8 \times 10^{-3}M$ in ligand.

Curve 0 and 0' represent the above titrations of the ligand and Cr(III) respectively.

FIG. 2. Distribution of chromium(III)-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate species as a function of hydrogen-ion concentration in the reaction mixture containing 1:1 molar ratios of the ligand and the metal ions (curve 1, Fig. 1). Curve 1: 1:1 chelate, CrA_2^+ . Curve 2: monohydroxy chelate $Cr(OH)A$.

TABLE III

KOH(ml)	..	0.0	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
pH	..	2.40	2.49	2.67	2.67	2.80	2.93
Log KMA_2	..	10.10	10.08	10.05	10.05	9.97	9.99

Mean of log $KMA_2 = 10.05$ or $KMA_2 = 1.12 \times 10^{10}$.

Appearance of a buffer region in the titration curve (curve 2, Fig. 1) after $m = 2$ indicates hydrolysis of the diaquo-chelate (III) (CrA_2^+) according to the reactions:

FIG. 3. Graphical demonstration of hydrolysis of the diaquo 2:1 chelate, CrA_2^+ , into monohydroxy Cr(OH)A_2^- and dihydroxy, $\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_3^-$ chelate species.

$$K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2} K_{\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_3} = 2 \times 10^{-17}$$

$$K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2} = 8.9 \times 10^{-8}$$

The gradual increasing slope of the titration curve indicates that the formation of the dihydroxo-chelate(V) does not take place in a single step, but there is overlapping between the two reactions, cited above. This has been tested by the graphical solution of the equilibria involved (equation 16, Fig. 3). The hydrolysis constants, $K_{\text{Cr(OH)A}_2} = 8.90 \times 10^{-8}$ and $K_{\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_3} = 2.24 \times 10^{-10}$ could thus be determined.

After determining the stability and the hydrolysis constants of the 2:1 chelate, the concentration of the various chelate species at various values of pH could be calculated under the experimental conditions (Fig. 4).

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FIG. 4. Distribution of Cr(III)-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate chelate species as a function of hydrogen-ion concentration in the reaction mixture containing 2:1 molar ratio of the ligand and the metal ions (curve 2, Fig. 1). Curve 1: normal 1:1 chelate CrA^+ . Curves 2 and 3: diaquo 2:1 chelate, CrA_2^+ . Curve 4: monohydroxy 2:1 chelate Cr(OH)A_2^- . Curve 5: dihydroxy 2:1 chelate, $\text{Cr(OH)}_2\text{A}_3^-$.